

SDHB/D: CanVIG-UK Gene-Specific Guidance

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For use in conjunction with CanVIG-UK Consensus Specification for Cancer susceptibility Genes of ACGS Best Practice Guidelines for Variant Classification. Evidence lines for which there are no gene-specific recommendations should be reviewed in context of CanVIG-UK Consensus Specification for Cancer Susceptibility Genes.

Evidence towards Pathogenicity

Evidence element and evidence strengths allowed	Thresholds/data-sources/applications specifically relevant to SDHB, SDHD																																										
<p>PS4: Case-control: The prevalence of the variant in affected individuals is significantly increased compared with the prevalence in controls</p>	<p>_VSTR _STR _MOD _SUP</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For variant data presented in Garrett et al 2021¹ (6,118 cases including data from Birmingham and Leeds NHS laboratories up to 2020; ethnicity of cases not all known) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> if variant frequency in gnomAD ≤ 1 in NFE and 0 in all other ethnicities in gnomAD and 1KGP <ul style="list-style-type: none"> →SUP if cases ≥ 2 ($p=0.002$), MOD if cases ≥ 4 ($p=0.000006$)* Where there are cases with the variant in addition to those included in Garrett et al 2021¹ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> if variant frequency in gnomAD ≤ 1 in NFE and =0 in all other ethnicities in gnomAD and 1KGP and cases are non-overlapping <ul style="list-style-type: none"> →SUP if cases ≥ 3, MOD if cases ≥ 5* <p>*These point allocations are very conservative to account for potential heterogeneity in case ethnicity and/or case ethnicities not represented in either gnomAD/1KGP</p>																																									
<p>PP4 (BP5): Phenotypic specificity/case counting (Patient's phenotype or family history is highly specific for a disease with a single genetic aetiology)</p>	<p>_VSTR _STR _MOD _SUP</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th colspan="2">Evidence points ^c</th> </tr> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th>SDHB</th> <th>SDHD</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Phaeochromocytoma/ paraganglioma (must meet PM2 MTAF)</td> <td></td> <td>+2</td> <td>+1</td> </tr> <tr> <td rowspan="2">Head & neck paraganglioma</td> <td>present</td> <td>+0.5</td> <td>+3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>absent</td> <td>-0.5</td> <td>-3</td> </tr> <tr> <td rowspan="2">Family history ^a</td> <td>present</td> <td>+3</td> <td>+4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>absent</td> <td>-</td> <td>-1</td> </tr> <tr> <td rowspan="2">Invasive disease</td> <td>present</td> <td>+2</td> <td>-</td> </tr> <tr> <td>absent</td> <td>-0.5</td> <td>-</td> </tr> <tr> <td rowspan="2">Multiple tumours</td> <td>present</td> <td>+0.5</td> <td>+2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>absent</td> <td>-</td> <td>-</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>				Evidence points ^c				SDHB	SDHD	Phaeochromocytoma/ paraganglioma (must meet PM2 MTAF)		+2	+1	Head & neck paraganglioma	present	+0.5	+3	absent	-0.5	-3	Family history ^a	present	+3	+4	absent	-	-1	Invasive disease	present	+2	-	absent	-0.5	-	Multiple tumours	present	+0.5	+2	absent	-	-
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<i>SDHB</i> immunohistochemistry (IHC)	loss	+3	+3
	normal	-1	-2
Succinate:Fumarate ratio (S:F) ^b	High (>97)	+3	+3
	Low (<97)	-	-

^a Presence of pheochromocytoma/paraganglioma in first/second degree relative

^b Validated assay performed in accredited diagnostic laboratory or laboratory publishing on S:F ratio. These evidence points have still been applied conservatively to account for variation in assay performance and lack of replication outside of reference publication.

^c Evidence points have been derived from the likelihood ratios in Garrett et al 2021¹. For the clinical subphenotypes, the LR_s from adjusted multiple regression have been used. The exponent of the lower 95th confidence interval has been used: where this is 0-1, it has been rounded to 0.5 where the point estimate of the exponent is >1. For negative LR_s/exponents (i.e. towards benignity), the upper 95th confidence interval is used.

Notes

- Points contributing to PP4/BP5 should be summed
- Where there are multiple cases with the variant reported clinically/in the literature, points for each clinical/molecular subphenotype (family history, head and neck, multiple tumours, invasive tumours, IHC loss, S:F ratio) can only be used once. Points for different subphenotypes can be awarded for different individuals/family members carrying the variant
- Where there are clinical data from multiple probands/family members that are discordant for a clinical subphenotype, only the positive score is counted (e.g. for a *SDHD* variant that has been reported 3 times, of which 1 is familial and two are isolated, 4 points are awarded).
- If there are conflicting data for two different IHC tests, no points should be awarded for IHC (S:F can still be awarded in this instance, independent of IHC). If IHC and S:F are discordant, the net score can be used. No more than 3 points can be awarded for the combination of IHC and S:F
- Points for LOH (as per consensus CanVIG guidance) can be awarded independently to (i.e. in addition to) IHC and S:F, as it is an orthogonal test
- If all the data for a variant come from a single case/family OR from a single-centre publication, points for PP4 should not exceed 4 (and the variant should not be classified at higher than likely pathogenic)

PM2: Absent from controls (or at extremely low frequency if recessive) in ESP, 1000GP, or ExAC

_MOD
_SUP

For PM2_mod frequency should be below predicted maximum tolerated allele frequency (MTAF) using the threshold below:

<i>SDHB</i>	<i>SDHD</i>
1.7×10^{-6}	7.3×10^{-7}

For PM2_sup follow main consensus specification recommendations ($\leq 0.002\%$ in a cancer-free control series of >50,000 individuals or any equivalent ratio in a larger control series)

PVS1: Predicted null variant (in a gene where LOF is a known mechanism of disease)

_VSTR
_STR
_MOD
_SUP

PS1: Same amino acid change as an established variant

_STR

_MOD

PM4: Protein-length-changing variant	_SUP													
PM5: Novel missense change at an amino acid residue where a different missense change determined to be pathogenic seen before	_MOD _SUP													
PP3: In silico: Multiple lines of computational evidence support a deleterious effect on the gene or gene product	_SUP													
PM1, PP2 (BP1): Enrichment/constraint: PP2: Missense variant in a gene that has a low rate of benign missense variation and in which missense variants are a common mechanism of disease PM1: Located in a mutational hot spot and/or critical and well-established functional domain (e.g. active site of an enzyme) without benign variation	_STR _MOD _SUP	<table border="1"> <tr> <td></td> <td>SDHB</td> <td>SDHD</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>aa 177-260</td> <td>aa 70-114</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Location within enriched region:</td> <td>+0.5</td> <td>+1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Location outside enriched region</td> <td>-</td> <td>-1</td> </tr> </table> <p>Additional notes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only apply if PP4 awarded for PHAEO/PGL+MTAF. • Where points contributing to PM1 are insufficient to attain PM1_supporting, points contributing to PM1 may be used in combination with points contributing to PP4 to increase evidence strength of PP4. 		SDHB	SDHD		aa 177-260	aa 70-114	Location within enriched region:	+0.5	+1	Location outside enriched region	-	-1
	SDHB	SDHD												
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Location within enriched region:	+0.5	+1												
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PS3: Functional: Well-established in vitro or in vivo functional studies supportive of a damaging effect on the gene or gene product	_VSTR _STR _MOD _SUP	No variant-specific ex-vivo assays established as robust.												
PP1: Co-segregation with disease in multiple affected family members in a gene definitively known to cause the disease	_VSTR _STR _MOD _SUP													
PS2/PM6: De novo (maternity and paternity confirmed/unconfirmed) in a patient with the disease and no family history	_STR _MOD _SUP													
PM3: in trans with a pathogenic variant (recessive disorders)	_STR _MOD _SUP													
PP5: Reputable source recently reports variant as pathogenic, but the evidence is not available to the laboratory to	_VSTR _STR _MOD _SUP													

perform an independent evaluation		
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Evidence towards Benignity

BA1/BS1: Allele frequency is “too high” in ExAC or gnomAD for disorder	_SA				
	_STR		SDHB	SDHD	
			BS1	1.7×10^{-6}	7.3×10^{-7}
			BA1	10^{-4}	10^{-4}
BS2: Observation in controls inconsistent with disease penetrance. Observed in a healthy adult individual for a recessive (homozygous), dominant (heterozygous), or X-linked (hemizygous) disorder, with full penetrance expected at an early age	_STR				
	_SUP				
BP4: In silico: Multiple lines of computational evidence suggest no impact on gene or gene product (conservation, evolutionary, splicing impact, etc.)	_SUP				
BP1: Missense variant in a gene for which primarily truncating variants are known to cause disease	_SUP				
BP7: Synonymous (silent) variant for which splicing prediction algorithms predict no impact to the splice consensus sequence	_SUP				
BP3: In-frame deletions/insertions in a repetitive region	_SUP				
BS3: Well-established <i>in vitro</i> or <i>in vivo</i> functional studies show no damaging effect on protein function or splicing	_STR				
	_MOD				
	_SUP				
BS4: Non segregation with disease	_STR				
	_SUP				
BP2: Observed in trans with a pathogenic variant for a fully penetrant dominant gene/disorder or observed in cis	_STR				
	_SUP				
BP6: Reputable source recently reports variant as benign, but the evidence is not available to the laboratory to perform an independent evaluation	_STR				
	_SUP				
BP5: Alternate molecular basis for disease	_SUP				

Version History/Amendments

Revised version	Date	Section	Update	Amended by	Approved by
1.1	04/03/22	All	Draft version for consultation with CanVIG	CT	CStAG
1.2	16/03/22	PP4	Addition of LOH Clarification of use of S:F in context of contradictory IHC	CT	CStAG
1.3	24/03/22	PM2	Application of PM2_sup as per main consensus guidance	AG	CStAG
1.4	18/03/25	PM1	Statement added to clarify use of points contributing to PM1 and PP4 in combination	SA	CStAG
1.4	18/03/25	PS4,PP4	Correction of typing errors	SA	CStAG

References

1. Garrett A, Loveday C, King L, et al. Quantifying evidence toward pathogenicity for rare phenotypes: The case of succinate dehydrogenase genes, SDHB and SDHD. *Genetics in Medicine* 2021;24(1):41-50. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gim.2021.08.004> [published Online First: 30 November 2021]